

Statistics of literature use of the term “spoiling” in gradient-echo MRI

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A set of publications were selected to examine the specification of the word “spoiling” (or “spoiled”). The was selection that was primarily drawn from references used in my PhD thesis and underlying publications. A further selection criterion was the presence of the string “spoil” (as in spoiling, spoiled, spoiler) in the context of gradient-echo sequences. Hits in references were not considered. This delivered over 80 hits. By a random selection, the set was further limited to 50 hits.

It was sorted on whether the term “spoiling”/“spoiled”/“spoiler” was accompanied by the specification “RF-”, “coherent gradient”, or that it was just tagged with “gradient”, or not specified at all.

Reference	Name of first author	RF-spoiling	Coherent gradient spoiling (context)	“gradient spoiling”	“spoiling”
1	Heule	*			
2	Bieri	*		*	
3	Amemiya	*			
4	Di Gugliano				“SPGR”
5	Jiang	*			
6	Heesterbeek		*		
7	Weiskopf	*			
8	MacKay				*
9	Aslander		*		
10	Keenan				*
11	Deoni				“SPGR”
12	Warntjes		*		
13	Kantola				*
14	Seif	context			
15	McDowell				*
16	Gao				*
17	Bieri	*			
18	Fujita				*
19	Aslander	*			
20	Jang	*			
21	Hamilton		*		
22	Rieger				*
23	Gomez	*			
24	Marty	context			
25	Fuderer			*	
26	Velasco				*
27	Qiao				“SPGR”
28	Ganter	*			
29	Weigel		*		
30	Mehta	*			
31	Buonincontri		*		

Reference	Name of first author	RF-spoiling	Coherent gradient spoiling (context)	“gradient spoiling”	“spoiling”
32	Buonincontri	*	*		
33	Sled				*
34	Gloor	context			
35	Teixeira	context			
36	Hilbert	*			
37	Pai				“SPGR”
38	Heule				*
39	Poorman		*		
40	Qiao		*		
41	Nolte			*	
42	McKenzie	*			
43	Körzdörfer			*	
44	Kobayashi		*		
45	Teixeira				“SPGR”
46	Weigel		*		
47	Mickevicius		*		
48	Leitao				*
49	Heesterbeek		*		
50	Van der Heide		*		

Table S1: In 50 references featuring “spoil” in the context of gradient-echo MRI, the type of spoiling is often specified, but often not. For RF-spoiling it is often made explicit (“*”); if “context” is mentioned, it is made clear within the same or subsequent paragraph. For coherent gradient spoiling, the context within the same paragraph may specify “SSFP”, “FISP” or be otherwise descriptive to clarify that coherent gradient spoiling is intended. Four references just tell “gradient spoiling” (which may be coherent or incoherent). Five specify it as “SPGR” (which may refer to RF-spoiling, incoherent gradient spoiling or a combination thereof). Lastly, 11 publications just tell “spoiling”.

From the table,

- 18 publications clearly refer to RF-spoiling (either explicitly or by immediate context).
- 14 publications refer to coherent gradient spoiling – as evident from immediate context.
- 4 publications refer to “gradient spoiling”, without further specification.
- 5 publications refer to “SPGR”.
- 11 just mention (unspecified) “spoiling”.

Further interesting side notes:

- Ref⁵ mentions RF-spoiled – as opposed to FISP, which is not called “spoiling” at all.
- Ref⁶ mentions “gradient spoiling” with reference to Jiang⁵ – a specification by reference.
- Ref⁹ mentions “gradient spoiling” as a characteristic of FISP, i.e. from the context, it refers to coherently spoiled. In this context, it is confusing to read that “FISP has a lower signal-to-noise ratio than SSFP”, which suggests that “SSFP” refers to a balanced sequence, which seems to contradict the nomenclature by Elster⁵¹.
- Ref¹² refers to “TFE, spoiled gradient echo”, which requires the knowledge of the Philips-acronym TFE to refer to coherently-spoiled.

- Ref ²⁵ shows that the author of this letter – in the past – violated against the advice of the letter to the editor.
- Ref ²⁸ specifies RF-spoiled, but features the sentence “RF spoiled SSFP” – whereas Zur⁵² considers “SSFP” and “RF spoiled” to be mutually exclusive.
- Ref ³⁴ is interesting, since it uses “Nonbalanced SSFP” in the title. Consistently, the word “spoiling” is avoided in the context of SSFP, such that when “spoiling” does appear, it is almost obvious that it refers to RF-spoiling.
- Ref ⁴⁶ refers to “spoiler and crusher gradients”. Interestingly, also the wording “in particular types of SSFP without RF spoiling” – suggesting that SSFP also *can* encompass RF spoiling. The sequence is otherwise sufficiently specified as “SSFP sequence and known as a FISP, GRASS, or FAST sequence (gradient spoiling but no RF spoiling)”
- Ref ⁴⁸ discusses “spoiled MRF (Jiang⁵)” – i.e. specification by reference

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